

Developmental Modulation of Cochlear Hair Bundle Membrane Viscosity Requires Functional Mechanotransduction Channel Complexes

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Abstract. Hair bundle deflection exerts force onto the tip-link that is translated to mechanically-gated (MET) ion channels located at the tops of the shorter stereocilia. There is a growing body of data suggesting that stereocilia membrane properties modulate MET channels. Our first direct assessment of membrane diffusivity using two-photon Fluorescent Recovery after Photobleaching (FRAP) demonstrated that the stereocilia membrane is more fluidic than the cell body membrane and is selectively sensitive to calcium and voltage. Transmembrane Channel-like proteins (TMCs) are implicated as part of the MET channel machinery, and recently are suggested to have membrane scramblase activity which regulates hair cell membrane homeostasis. To further investigate the role of membrane in modulating MET channel behavior, we developed the technology to use a novel viscosity sensor BODIPY 1c whose changes in fluorescence lifetime allows precise spatial and dynamic monitoring of membrane properties within live hair cells. Serendipitously, we found that BODIPY1c also enters hair cells through open MET channels, fluorescently labelling cytoplasmic membranes that allows identification of hair cells with functional MET channels. We show that mammalian cochlear hair cell stereocilia membrane viscosity reduces during development. Membrane viscosity decreases and strongly correlates with the onset of MET. Next, we tested whether MET channel complex proteins were required for the changes in stereocilia membrane properties. TMIE is required for transport and maintenance of the MET machinery proteins while also considered a critical component of the MET machinery. The membrane viscosity of stereocilia in the TMIE knockout mouse remained elevated at levels similar to that of immature stereocilia. Together these data suggest that stereocilia membrane viscosity is modulated during development with a time course that correlates with the onset of MET. Lack of TMIE prevents the reduction in viscosity. MET machinery could be directly impacting the membrane through their putative scramblase activity. It is also plausible that the membrane changes are a direct and/or indirect effect of MET current or calcium entry. Further studies are ongoing to better understand these mechanisms and the functional relevance between TMCs, membrane viscosity and MET.

INTRODUCTION

The mechano-electrical transduction (MET) process is the process by which hair cells translate mechanical stimulation of their hair bundle into electrical signal. The hair bundles are the sensory organelle located on the apical surface of the hair cells and are comprised of three rows of actin-filled stereocilia. Extracellular filamentous structures, termed tip links, connect shorter stereocilia to their neighboring taller stereocilia such that hair bundle deflection toward the tallest stereocilia pulls the tip link, exerting force at the stereocilia tip. This force causes MET channels, located at the top of the shorter stereocilia [1], to open allowing for ion flux. The MET channel complex, containing at least TMC1/2,

TMIE and LHFPL5[2-5], are likely mechanically coupled to the lower tip link protein PCDH15 proteins and to the cytoskeleton through proteins like Cib2[6, 7]. The upper tip link, composed of CDH23, is similarly coupled to the cytoskeleton through proteins such as Harmonin and Sans [8, 9]. The mechanical properties of the lipid bilayer will influence those molecules which span or are coupled to the membrane.

Most mechanically gated channels such as MscL, MscS, TRAAK1, TREK-1, PIEZO1 are sensitive to force translated through the membrane[10-13]. Likely tethered, hair cell MET channels could be sensing force translated through the membrane differently than the stretch activated channels which are not tethered. There is a limited but growing body of data on lipid modulation of hair cell MET. A stretch-activated channel modifier, GsMTx4, shifts the MET activation (current-displacement) curve rightward, decreasing the MET channel resting open probability (P_o) similar to its effect on PIEZO1 and stretch-activated channels, and blocks the leftward shift in the activation plot induced by lowering external calcium or hair cell depolarization [14]. PIP2, an endogenous lipid, modulates MET channel conductance, open probability, and kinetics [15]. TMCs are implicated as part of the MET channel machinery, and recently are suggested to have membrane scramblase activity which regulates hair cell membrane homeostasis [16].

Our recent direct assessment of membrane diffusivity using two-photon Fluorescent Recovery after Photobleaching (FRAP) demonstrated that the stereocilia membrane is highly diffusive as compared to the soma and stereocilia diffusivity is preferentially sensitive to calcium and voltage compared to the soma [17]. This data further shows that MET channel P_o co-varies with membrane diffusivity, supporting the hypothesis that MET channels are modulated by membrane mechanics. This data represents the first demonstration of calcium dependent modulation of stereocilia membrane diffusivity. However, due to spatial and temporal limitations of FRAP, we were unable to monitor stereocilia membrane both locally and dynamically.

To further investigate the role of membrane in modulating MET channel behavior, we developed the technology to use a novel viscosity-sensitive “molecular rotor” BODIPY 1c (fig. 1C) based on fluorescence lifetime imaging (FLIM) that allows precise spatial and dynamic monitoring of membrane properties within live hair cells. Molecular rotors are small synthetic fluorophores that exhibit viscosity-dependent fluorescence quantum yield and fluorescence lifetime i.e., the average time a fluorophore remains in the excited state [18-21]. Rotation or intramolecular twisting of molecular rotor leads to non-radiative decay from the excited state back to the ground state. In an ordered or more viscous membrane, the non-radiative decay pathway is restricted leading to an increase in the fluorescence intensity and fluorescence lifetime and in less viscous membrane, the fluorescence intensity and lifetime decreases.

As the cochlear MET matures over several days during development, we first examined whether stereocilia membrane viscosity changes during development. We found that mammalian cochlear hair cell stereocilia membrane viscosity reduces during development, in contrast to supporting cells, and strongly correlates with the onset of MET. We then examined if the lack of MET complex proteins affects the developmental changes in the membrane. Lack of TMIE, a protein that is a critical component of the MET channel complex and is required for transport and maintenance of the MET channel proteins, prevents the reduction in viscosity. Our data suggests that functional MET machinery is required for the developmental changes in the membrane viscosity. MET channel could be directly impacting the membrane through their

putative scramblase activity and/or indirectly through the MET current and/or calcium entry. We are currently conducting further studies to understand the connection between MET channel machinery and membrane mechanics.

METHODS

Sample Preparation

Glycerol/methanol mixture preparation: The lifetime of BODIPY 1c was calibrated as a function of viscosity using glycerol/ methanol mixtures varying from 30:70 to 95:5. BODIPY 1c was added to the 2 ml glycerol/methanol mixture at 1:500 rotor:mixture ratio and kept on a rotating vertical mixture at RT, away from the light, overnight for efficient mixing. For imaging, the glycerol/methanol mixture was transferred to a glass well plate.

Vesicle preparation: Artificial lipid vesicles were used as a control for validating BODIPY 1c dye properties. Liposomes were prepared with either 100% 1,2-dioleoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DOPC, Avanti Polar Lipids) or 70% Egg Sphingomyelin (Egg SM, Avanti Polar Lipids, 860061).and 30% Cholesterol (Ovine Cholesterol, Avanti Polar lipids, 700000). Dried lipids were hydrated in the buffer with 100 mM KCl and 10 mM HEPES at pH 7.4 for an hour. The lipid solution was then extruded (Mini Extruder, Avanti Polar Lipids) through a 200 nm polycarbonate membrane 11 times. BODIPY 1c was added to the lipid solution in 1:200 rotor:lipid ratio and kept at 4°C, away from light. For imaging, the liposomes were mounted on a slide in 0.5% agarose gel (Fisher Scientific) to keep them mechanically stable.

Cochlear explants: Sprague-Dawley rats (Charles River Laboratories) and *Tmie^{KO}* (B6.B(CBA)-*Tmie^{sr}*/J, JAX 000543) were used in the experiments. For mice, heterozygous littermates served as controls. Animals were sacrificed by decapitation and cochlear turn of isolated organ of Corti was dissected from pups at postnatal day 1 (P1) and P10 as described previously [22]. Briefly, temporal bones were removed from the skull and cochlear tissue was placed in extracellular solution containing (in mM): 142 NaCl, 2 KCl, 2 CaCl₂, 1 MgCl₂, 10 HEPES, 6 Glucose, 2 Ascorbate /Pyruvate, 2 Creatine monohydrate, at pH 7.4 and a final osmolality of 304 - 307 mOsm. The tissue was incubated with 10 μM of BODIPY (boron dipyrin) 1c in extracellular solution at room temperature (RT) for 6 mins, protected from light. The tissue was then transferred to the recording chamber with dye-free extracellular solution and held in place with single strands of dental floss while ensuring that inner hair cell (IHC) bundles were oriented vertically. During the experiment, tissue was perfused with extracellular solution at rate of 0.3 ml/min maintained at RT.

Fluorescence Lifetime Imaging (FLIM)

FLIM experiments using BODIPY 1c were carried out using an upright Leica TCS-SP8 FALCON (FASt Lifetime CONtrast) confocal microscope using LAS-X version 3.5.6 software (Leica Microsystems GmbH, Germany) and an HC PL APO 20x / 1.0 NA water dipping objective (Leica Microsystems GmbH, Germany). The excitation source was a pulsed white light laser (WLL). BODIPY 1c was excited at 480 nm and the pulse repetition frequency of the laser was set to 40 MHz. Two sensitive hybrid detectors

(SMD, Leica Microsystems CMS GmbH, Germany) allowed for photon detection from 490-560 nm and 600-670 nm. A frame accumulation of 50 was set to allow better photon statistics FLIM images were acquired at 512×512 pixel in the XY direction. Z-stacks were captured at 1 μ m step interval.

FLIM Analysis

All FLIM images were analyzed using LAS X FLIM/FCS version 3.5.6 software. Each ROI consisted of a hair bundle on a single z-plane. The fluorescence decay curves were fitted using n-exponential reconvolution with IRF (instrument response function) model. The function of this model is:

$$y(t) = \{IRF(t+Shift_{IRF})\} \otimes \left\{ \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} A[i] e^{\left(-\frac{t}{\tau[i]}\right)} + Bkgr \right\},$$

where A is the amplitudes, τ is the lifetimes, n is the number of exponential components, *Bkgr* is the tail offset (correction for background), and *Shift_{IRF}* is the IRF shift (correction for IRF displacement). For the hair bundles, the decay curves were best fitted by a biexponential model with the goodness of fit parameter (χ^2) >1. The average of the two intensity-weighted lifetime components were calculated by:

$$\tau_{Av,Int} = \frac{\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} I[k]\tau[k]}{I_{Sum}},$$

where *Isum* is the sum of the fluorescence intensity of all components. The intensity-weighted average lifetime represents the mean photon arrival time and hence we report this value in this paper for all the experiments.

RESULTS

BODIPY 1c has been calibrated previously by the lab that designed it [21], but we characterized the BODIPY 1c that we synthesized for our lab by Nanosyn under our experimental conditions and with our imaging systems. The lifetime of BODIPY 1c increased with increasing content of glycerol in glycerol/methanol mixture confirming that the lifetime of BODIPY 1c increases with increasing viscosity (fig. 1A). Similarly, the highly viscous SM:Chol vesicles showed higher lifetime than pure DOPC vesicles (fig. 1B), thus validating BODIPY 1c.

Following calibration and validation of BODIPY 1c, we implemented BODIPY 1c in the organ of Corti after determining the optimal concentration and incubation time. Figure 1D shows FLIM images of inner hair cell (IHC) hair bundles from P10 rat mid-apical turn focused on the first row and second row of stereocilia with ring-like stereocilia membrane visible. The fluorescence decay of BODIPY 1c in the hair bundles at 20°C was best fitted with a biexponential model indicating that the molecular rotor is probing the heterogeneities in the stereocilia membrane. Using the time constants extracted from the biexponential decay, we report the intensity-weighted mean lifetime to represent the average lifetime.

Figure 1: Calibration and validation of BODIPY 1c in our lab. A) shows fluorescence lifetime of BODIPY 1c in glycerol/methanol mixtures of varying viscosities at 21°C. Corresponding FLIM images are shown at the top. B) shows DOPC vesicle (low viscosity) with lower lifetime for BODIPY 1c compared to EYSM/Chol vesicles (high viscosity). Scale bar = 2 μ m. C) shows the molecular structure of BODIPY 1c highlighting the part of the structure that undergoes rotation or intramolecular twisting at the excited state. D) FLIM of BODIPY 1c in organ of Corti (apical turn) of P10 rat showing the IHB focused on the 1st row and 2nd row stereocilia. Scale bar = 5 μ m.

Cochlear hair bundles undergo structural and functional maturation over several days during development. Along with the changes in hair bundle height and shape, the mechanosensitivity matures with current amplitude increasing during development [23]. Therefore, we investigated if the hair bundle membrane viscosity changes during development and whether the viscosity correlates with the onset of MET.

Figure 2: A) FLIM images of developing rat organ of Corti stained with BODIPY 1c from the cochlear mid-apical turn at P1 and P10 focusing on the hair bundles (top row) and soma (bottom row). B) Quantification of the mean lifetime showing significantly lower lifetime for HC bundle at P10 compared to P1 (*t* test, $p < 0.001$). The supporting pillar cells (PCs) show no change from P1 to P10 (*t* test, $p > 0.05$). Scale bar = 10 μ m.

At P1 mid-apical turn, the OHC bundles showed higher lifetime (red hair bundles; fig. 2A top left panel) and the IHC bundles showed higher and lower lifetimes (red and green hair bundles; fig. 2A top

left panel). At P10, both the OHC and IHC bundles showed lower lifetime (green; fig. 2A top right panel). Images focused on the soma show that the absence of BODIPY 1c in the hair cells with red bundles indicating non-transducing hair bundles and increase in the BODIPY 1c signal as the lifetime is reduced at P10 (fig. 2A bottom panels). We didn't observe this change in the supporting pillar cells (PCs). This shows that the viscosity of the hair bundles significantly reduces during development, and it correlates with the onset of MET (fig. 2A, B).

We then explored whether the lack of MET channel complex in the hair bundle would affect the stereocilia membrane. For this purpose, we captured FLIM images of organ of Corti of the homozygous spinner *Tmie^{KO/KO}* mice [24] which lack TMIE, a subunit contributing to the channel pore and is required for localization of TMC1 and TMC2 to the hair bundle [2, 25, 26]. In the *Tmie^{KO/KO}* mice, the hair bundles in

Figure 3: A) FLIM images taken from P10 mid-apical turns of *Tmie^{+KO}* and *Tmie^{KO/KO}* mice focusing on the hair bundles (top and middle rows) and supporting pillar cells (bottom row). B) The *Tmie^{KO/KO}* has significantly higher lifetime for the HC bundles than the littermate *Tmie^{+KO}* (*t* test, $p < 0.001$) while the PC soma showed no difference between the groups at P10. Scale bar = 10 μ m.

both the OHCs and the IHCs showed significantly higher lifetime (fig. 3) compared to the littermate controls, *Tmie^{+KO}*. The images focused on the soma of the HCs showed the absence of 1c in the cytoplasm of the *Tmie^{KO/KO}* compared to the littermate controls, confirming that the dye couldn't enter the soma of this MET channel complex mutant. No significant difference was observed between the PC soma of the *Tmie^{KO/KO}* and the *Tmie^{+KO}* and WT mice suggesting that the effect on the membrane viscosity is specific to the HCs.

To test whether the difference in the membrane viscosity is contributed by the presence of cholesterol, we used the antibiotic filipin, a fluorescent cholesterol-binding molecule, to localize cholesterol with the hair bundles [27]. Even though both groups showed strong and similar staining along the lengths of the hair bundle (fig. 4A), the intensity quantification showed that mutant bundles have higher peak intensity position than the controls (fig. 4B). However, it is unlikely that such a small change in cholesterol level is enough to account for the big change in the viscosity of the *Tmie^{KO/KO}* hair bundles. There could be other factors that would be attributed to the higher viscosities in the mutants.

Figure 4: A) Filipin labelling of P10 mid-apical turns of *Tmie*^{+/*+*} and *Tmie*^{KO/*KO*} mice focusing on the OHC and IHC hair bundles B) Quantification of the peak intensity position of filipin staining showing significant difference between both the groups (*t* test, *p* < 0.001). Scale bar = 5 μ m.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

Current spectroscopic methods available to measure membrane properties fall short of either measuring microscopic regions in space or are difficult to implement in auditory hair bundles due to its unique structure. Here, we implemented a new technology based on FLIM of a viscosity sensor, for the first time in the inner ear, that will allow precise spatial and dynamic imaging of micromembrane properties within individual stereocilium of live hair cells. Using the viscosity sensor, we show that the stereocilia membrane viscosity, and not supporting cell (pillar cell) viscosity, decreases during development with the onset of MET. Lack of TMIE/MET machinery prevents the reduction in viscosity.

Both IHC and OHC hair bundles show significantly high membrane viscosity during the earlier days of development when they are immature and non-transducing. High membrane viscosity may arise due to lipid composition, protein content, membrane interaction with underlying cytoskeletal structures, MET machinery and/or active lipid transport by flippases and floppases [28]. There has been no systematic study on the hair bundle lipid composition during developmental time course, and especially in mammals at the age that we measured membrane viscosity. Lipid mass spectrometry of embryonic day 20 (E20)-E21 chick vestibular hair bundles suggests that PC, cholesterol and PE accounts for 86% and PS, SM and PI make up 12% of the lipid detected in the hair bundles with the hair bundle lipid composition not significantly different from the whole organs [27]. Compartmentalization of specific lipids or even high

levels of some lipids can have dramatic effects on membrane mechanics; therefore, we cannot completely exclude lipid composition as a contributor.

Stereocilia membrane viscosity reduces during development and correlates strongly with the onset of MET. TMCs are implicated as part of the MET channel machinery, and recently are suggested to have membrane scramblase activity which regulates hair cell membrane homeostasis [16]. TMC proteins are reported to be structurally related to TMEM 16, a family of Ca^{2+} activated lipid scramblases and channels [29]. Lipid scramblases provide a permeation pathway for the diffusion of phospholipids between the plasma membrane leaflets following their concentration gradient. Recent ongoing work by another group suggests that lipid scrambling induces membrane softening i.e., reduces membrane packing and stiffness [30]. Therefore, it is likely that TMCs are providing lipid scrambling to reduce the membrane viscosity. It is also possible that the reduced viscosity is a function of voltage, MET current and/or calcium entry with the onset of MET. The effects of voltage and calcium may be acting through changes in the membrane mechanical properties, due to multivalent ions binding between adjacent lipids to alter the lipid order or packing [31-33].

Studies of other mechanosensitive channels show that decreased membrane fluidity increases their activation threshold, and thinner membrane favors channel opening [34, 35]. In contrast, our previous study showed that stereociliary membrane diffusivity is generally high while the MET resting P_o is low, and the P_o increases as diffusivity is reduced [17], at least in the range of measured diffusivity. In this study, the membrane viscosity is reducing (i.e., membrane fluidity is increasing) with the onset of MET. The opposite polarity for hair cell MET channel sensitivity may be simply due to how force is transmitted to the MET channel. While many mechanosensitive channels sense force transmitted directly through the membrane, hair cell channels are thought to be tethered to both an extracellular and intracellular link [36]. Thus, the membrane is potentially being locally regulated for the channel to be more sensitive and faster.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Catalina, Valez]: Looks like you had the resolution at least in the inner hair cells to look at positions around stereocilia. Did you see difference between top and bottom in terms of viscosity?

[Shefin, George]: I performed some 3D reconstruction from the z-stack FLIM images but so far, I haven't seen any difference between the tip of the stereocilia compared to the rest of the hair bundle. I do see that some regions along the length have higher viscosity.

[Cataline, Valez]: How about between the tallest and shorter stereocilia?

[Shefin, George]: No, they both seem to be the same.

[Jong-Hoon, Nam]: I wonder if you think membrane viscosity is related to the adaptation.

[Shefin, George]: We are definitely interested in investigating that. Currently, the temporal resolution of the system limits us from looking into it. I have been working on implementing point scanning to follow a target region like maybe at the tip of the stereocilia. I strongly think sometime soon, we can answer some of those questions and that is a direction that I'm interested in as well.

[Jong-Hoon, Nam]: Did you see any tonotopic differences in the membrane viscosity?

[Shefin, George]: I do think there is a slight difference, but I need to quantify those values. The differences are not as significant as what we see during development though. I do believe there is a difference of 0.2-0.3 ns but it needs quantification.

[Martin, Toderi]: Have you tested the toxicity of the dye in the cells?

[Shefin, George]: Oh yes absolutely. One of the major issues with the sensor is that if used in higher concentration, it can aggregate and underestimate the measurements. I did spend a lot of time determining the best incubation time and concentration for the hair cells.

[Martin, Toderi]: So, you're saying that these cells are alive but when you're doing FLIM you are collecting the photons for a while. How long is that?

[Shefin, George]: It depends on the size of the region obviously. These images that I presented today would take 3-4 mins. If I want to image a single or a couple of bundles, I can go as fast as 300ms.

[Martin, Toderi]: I was thinking about looking at local changes in the membrane viscosity, like live changes. So that would be possible, right?

[Shefin, George]: Yes, that would be possible. This sensor has both its lifetime and intensity sensitive to the viscosity of the environment. The intensity measurements can be really fast if performed in point scanning mode and I would lean towards 2 photon as that would be gentle on the cells.